

**EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT
AND WAYS TO USE THEM**

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Abstract. *In this article The priority development of farms as the main product-producing entity in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan in the future is highlighted as the basis for a detailed study of the activities of the US Department of Agriculture and the Ministry of Agriculture in the People's Republic of China, where the farming movement is widely developed*

Keywords: *Agriculture, production, activities, consumption, foreign, finance, guaranteed prices, budget, laws, country, payments, import, ,management, financial resources..*

In the US, federal and state departments of agriculture implement agricultural policy. But they operate independently, the interaction between them is regulated by federal laws. However, the US Department of Agriculture has a powerful influence on production and consumption in every state of the country. These are implemented at the expense of programs financed from the federal budget. They can be divided into four groups: guaranteed prices, limitation of cultivated area, direct payments, import quotas.

All federal programs adopted in the United States are provided with financial resources that allow attracting material, technical and labor resources necessary for their implementation.

In order to implement the government policy on maintaining the level of prices of agricultural products, the Commodity Credit Corporation (TKK) was established within the Federal Department of Agriculture. TKK provides loans to farmers for the cultivation of a number of commodities, the rates of which are fixed for each commodity.

In October 1994, the United States Department of Agriculture was structurally restructured as part of the overall government reform plan. This department was created for the purpose of "collecting and disseminating useful information on US agriculture in a broad sense."

The structural restructuring of the department was carried out on the basis of the following principles:

- orientation of agriculture to market relations; assisting farmers in increasing farm income; development of rural areas; providing the population with food products; ensure food safety; focus on issues of environmental protection; scientific support for all decisions on agrarian policy.

The department operates in 9 directions:

- programs for farmers and foreign agriculture; economic development of rural areas; food, consumption and consumer services; natural resources and environment; science, education and economics; food safety; marketing and control; Relations with the US Congress; administrative matters.

As a result of this event, 3.6 billion dollars. savings were made, 11,000 people were laid off, the number of central hardware departments was reduced from 43 to 27, and 1,100 departments were closed across the country.

Currently, the Federal Law "On Reform and Improvement of Agriculture" adopted by the US Congress in 1996 is in force in the USA, and federal budget funds are allocated for its implementation. Its main aspects relate to the following areas of agricultural development:

- plant breeding; prospective agrarian policy; dairy farming; food consumption; conservation of natural resources; development of rural areas; research works.

The application of the positive aspects of the agricultural management experience in developed countries, including the USA, which are suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan, plays an important role in improving the network management system, increasing its efficiency and ensuring the manageability of agriculture.

The Ministry of Agriculture, established in 1949 in the People's Republic of China, was structurally reorganized. The Ministry is empowered to study and analyze the general situation in the industry based on the state's economic strategic plans for agriculture, to implement and organize the implementation of the established plans.

The Ministry of Agriculture of the People's Republic of China is authorized to prepare and submit proposals for consideration by the government on issues such as financial support for agriculture, animal husbandry and fisheries, the implementation of the program for the gradual introduction of industry into agriculture, as well as the establishment of districts of new forms of agricultural enterprises. enters. The Ministry participates in the preparation of standards and technical norms for the quality of agricultural and livestock products. The Ministry is considered an authorized body of the State Council of the People's Republic of China:

Agricultural economics; planting and care of agricultural products; water management; land development; fodder production; mechanization of agriculture; organizes, manages and controls the implementation of scientific developments in agriculture.

The Ministry to carry out the above tasks:

1. Analyzes, studies and plans agricultural development strategy and rural economy, develops medium-term and long-term development programs, organizes project implementation, plans agricultural production programs after approval by the State Council of the People's Republic of China.

2. Research and planning of various sub-sectors of agriculture based on political guidelines and guidelines; efficient use of agricultural resources and their deployment; improving the quality of products; making proposals on taxing and price management of agricultural products; efficient use of production and working capital, loans; control of tax deductions and financial subsidies of agricultural organizations; Active participation in the development of relevant draft laws of the PRC; performs work on the analysis of the area of agricultural crops, the state of crops and their care, livestock, water management, agricultural enterprises and other sub-sectors.

3. Deepening the reorganization of agriculture, development of the social sector, organization of collective, cooperative (company) enterprises, consolidation and improvement of the management system (in accordance with the established instructions of the Center), policy of agricultural management, simplification of the system of granting the right to use arable land to farmers, workers control and management of training development.

4. On the basis of the political guidelines, it carries out the study and development of the following programs: improving the introduction of industry into agriculture; formation and

development of market relations for the main types of products; development and coordination of the "vegetable basket" project; use of means of production.

To study the import and export of the main types of agricultural products and means of production, to make proposals on this matter; sales of the main types of products and means of production, determining the forecast of demand for them and preparing data, as well as preparing various other information on agriculture.

5. Organization of work on the distribution of agricultural resources by region; considers the issues of ecological improvement, agricultural lands, reservoirs in areas specializing in fishing, deserts, marshes, swamps and dry lands, as well as effective use and development of other resources in agriculture, protection of biological resources, ecological protection of water resources in fishing areas.

6. To lead scientific and research work on agriculture, to select and implement the most basic research and technical projects.

7. Establishing technical standards for fish products caught in different basins, quality control of ecologically clean products, selection and protection of new varieties of crops, inspection and examination of the quality of seeds, chemicals, mineral fertilizers.

8. Drafting rules and laws on quarantine and anti-epidemic measures, establishing relevant standards, establishing veterinary regulations, carrying out anti-epidemic measures, quarantine work and parasite eradication.

9. Organizes intergovernmental dialogues, signs agreements, such as international economic or technical exchange in the field of agriculture.

10. Reforming enterprises and leading the activities of farms in their system, increasing state capital in them.

11. Implementation of the current work on the organization of assistance to the poor by the State Council group.

12. To engage in other activities based on the instructions of the State Council of the People's Republic of China.

The analysis shows that the country monitors and summarizes almost all processes in agriculture.

Agricultural producers in all countries operate under difficult conditions. They are opposed by the monopolized industry that manufactures and supplies the means of production for agriculture, large trading firms, food industry enterprises and other market structures.

It is known from foreign experience that without state support and structures protecting the interests of rural producers (association, union, association), they will not have the opportunity to work on an equal footing with large firms.

In different countries, the problem of organizing self-government was solved in its own way. For example, the experience of the United Kingdom, the United States, France and other developed countries shows that in the agricultural sector, along with the state management system, a vertical economic management system of industry unions, associations, councils, cooperatives and other forms of organizations operates.

France. Among the developed western countries, the experience of French agricultural management is of particular importance for Uzbekistan, because various methods of effective management are used in this country in optimal proportions. In France, family farms are the basis of agriculture and their number is about 1 million. is ten.

The Supreme Council for the direction and coordination of the development of the agricultural and food industry is the highest body for the coordination of intersectoral relations in the French agro-food complex. The Council includes representatives of the Ministries of Finance, Industry, Agriculture and Forestry, and enterprises in the fields of sale and processing of agricultural products. It is responsible for the development of measures to improve the organization and management of sub-complexes, the participants of the production and sale system, and the main directions of agrarian policy, attracting financial resources, introducing scientific and technical achievements, and determining the ways of development of foreign economic activity. performs tasks such as developing the order of relations between representatives.

The scope of authority of the Supreme Council includes organizations that carry out the regulation of the internal market of agricultural products, allocation of subsidies for product storage, processing and export, purchase of agricultural products at guaranteed prices.

The French agri-food sector is managed by the Ministry of Agriculture and Water, its regional and departmental units, the Chambers of Agriculture, as well as a number of mixed, parastatal and professional structures of a sectoral and intersectoral nature.

The latter included representatives of farmers, processing industry, trade, cooperatives, and professional organizations along with civil servants. In this way, a unified system was created for determining the directions of agricultural development and managing the markets of agricultural products. Among the agricultural management bodies, only the government takes appropriate decisions under the partial influence of the Parliament and the Chamber of Agriculture. Specialized bodies (state and non-state) perform consultative, informational and coordinating functions.

The main functions of the Ministry of Agriculture include the coordination of financial, administrative and technical activities in the field of food processing and forestry, including the wood processing industry.

It carries out the tasks of conducting scientific research, improving the system of education and professional training, commenting on the laws and guidelines regulating relations in agriculture, providing the state with extensive information on its activities in the agricultural sector.

The Ministry studies the problems of development of agricultural and tariff policy, influence on the market of agricultural products, promotion of export of products. It performs tasks related to quality control of food products, protection of flora and fauna, and international cooperation in the field of food complex. Before making decisions on agrarian policy issues for the implementation of which state funds are required, the Ministry must obtain the approval of the Ministry of Finance.

In France, the structure of the ministry reflects the functions assigned to it. In order to fulfill the assigned tasks, the ministry includes 9 departments with a narrow range of specialized structural units.

At the local level, the management of the French food sector is carried out by 22 regional and 100 departmental administrations. The process of decentralization, expansion of the rights of communes, departments, and regions had an impact on their activities. Since 1990, agricultural departments have been operating independently, separating their powers and funds from other departments.

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Regional and departmental administrations work closely with processing industry, farmers and other categories of rural population.

One of the characteristics of the French system of agricultural management is the high proportion of agricultural enterprises of different branches and professional descriptions. Among them, two subjects have a great influence on the formation of agrarian policy - the agricultural chambers and the system of trade unions.

Chambers of Agriculture are state institutions formed on the basis of elections. They act as mediators between farms and state authorities. Elections to the chambers are held under the leadership of the prefectures. Chambers of Agriculture operate as consultation centers under state authorities of relevant departments.

They provide information to government authorities about the state of agricultural development. Chamber members are elected from among farmers, their family members, hired workers of farms or agricultural enterprises, large landowners, members of cooperatives, employees of credit and insurance institutions. Also, one or more administrative staff of forestry centers are permanent members of agricultural chambers.

All members of the Agricultural Chambers are elected for 6 years and may be re-elected for a new term. The number of members of chambers can be from 34 to 48 depending on the department. More than 3,000 consultants and specialists work in the chambers, participating in the implementation of long-term programs for the development of agricultural production. The organizational structure of agricultural chambers consists of three independent and non-subordinate levels. At the lower level, there are 94 departmental chambers that protect the interests of producers and meet the specific needs of the respective department.

Regional agricultural chambers consisting of representatives of departmental chambers operate in each region. They determine and agree on regional agrarian policy. The advisory functions of regional chambers relate to problems in the field of economic, professional education, territorial structure and environmental protection, communications. At the national level, there is a permanent assembly of the Chambers of Agriculture, which unites the presidents of all the chambers. It develops an approach to national and European agricultural policy, makes proposals for solving problems in the field of land relations and taxation. The permanent assembly is in direct contact with the president of the republic, the government and the parliament. The parliamentary communication service of the Permanent Assembly conveys the views of agricultural enterprises on the problems that have arisen to the higher state authorities, participates in the discussion of these problems. Chambers of Agriculture and their Permanent Assembly exercise their authority during sessions (twice a year) attended by representatives of the authorities and heads of relevant administrative bodies, as well as through their representatives in other national, regional and departmental offices, which are obliged to take into account the opinion of state power structures.

Decisions of the Chambers of Agriculture and the Assembly are adopted by majority vote and submitted to the Minister of Agriculture. Chambers of agriculture have the status of a public organization, are considered legal entities and conduct independent financial activities. They not only protect the interests of agricultural enterprises, but can also organize and subsidize them, be members of joint-stock companies, agricultural cooperatives and associations.

The budget of the Chambers of Agriculture is formed at the expense of taxes, subsidies, consumer obligations and loans paid by landowners. The size of the tax is determined annually

by the chambers. Subsidies are allocated to Chambers of Agriculture by the National Fund for the Development of Agriculture, formed from indirect taxes on products, as well as from the funds of regional and general councils. Usually, these structures participate in specific targeted programs, but do not fully finance such projects.

In the financing of long-term programs, the share of the National Fund for Agricultural Development is 25%, chambers - 25%, and farmers' own funds - 50%.

Chamber members are representatives of departmental committees and commissions: agricultural structure development commission, land formation commission, professional training and employment committee, transport committee, natural disaster prevention committee, etc. Chambers of agriculture can organize special services (financial-estimate, legal, economic), as well as participate in services organized in cooperation with other organizations (cooperatives, syndicates, associations, etc.).

Summarizing foreign experiences allows us to distinguish the general directions of creating a hierarchy of economic management:

- the principles of network and territorial structure of economic structures are compatible with each other;
- mainly a two-level vertical structure is used;
- the activity is primarily focused on product sales and price regulation;
- at the national level, industry unions unite in an inter-industry organization that protects the common interests of farmers in the government and parliament;
- economic structures rely on the support of political parties in their activities;
- distributes quotas and state subsidies for the production of necessary products through industry unions;
- in some countries, scientific research institutes are part of industry unions.

Conclusion: The practice of agricultural enterprises of our country shows that in the current conditions, an individual enterprise cannot get out of the economic crisis by itself. Therefore, in order to develop entrepreneurship in agriculture, along with the state management system, it is necessary to have an independent vertical structure of economic management from the farm to the republic level, assuming that the owner has the right to create his own private management system.

Implementation of the above will allow to create an optimal organizational structure of agricultural management in the republic, to clearly define the tasks of management subjects at different levels of management, and as a result, to increase production efficiency.

REFERENCES

1. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 4th con. Page 179.A. Dyzhov “Fundamentals of intellectual property management”. Mogilev - 2007.-117p.
2. SD Ilyenkova Innovation management. — M.: UNITI-DANA, 2008. — 105 p. Innovative management: textbook. allowance / N.P. Makarkin, L.V. Shaborkin. - Saransk: publishing house of Mordov. Univ.- 1997.- 80s.
3. B.I.Komiljonov “Innovation management uslublarin takomillashtirish”. 2007
4. Porter M. International competition: Per. from English / Ed. by V.D. Shchetinina. - M. International relations, 1993. - 64 p.;

5. Bright I.R. Some Management Lessons from Technological Innovation Research, National Conference on Management of Technological Innovation, University of Bradford Management Centre, 1968.;
6. Twiss B. Management of scientific and technical innovations: abbr. per. English/Aut. foreword other ed. K.F. Bubble. - M.: Economics, 1989. - 31 p.; Latechnologieetl'economie: Lesrelationdeterminantes. P.: OECD, 1992.
7. Santo B. Innovation as a means of economic development: Per. from Hung. / Common. ed. and entry .st. B.V. Sazonova. – M.: Progress, 1990. – 296 p.
8. Fatkhudinov R.A. Innovation management.: Textbook for universities. - MCJSC "Business School" Intel-sintez "", 1998.- 17p.
9. Abdullaev R.V., Khasanjanov K.A. Innovative renewal of the economy - the basis of its modernization and competitiveness //
10. Strategy of socio-economic development of the agro-industrial complex of the Russian Federation for the period up to 2020. (scientific foundations). Russian Academy of Agricultural Sciences. M., 2011
11. U.M.Umurzakov, A.J.Toshboev, "Economy of farms". T: Tashkent. 2009.
12. www.tandfonline.com;
13. www.sidra.ibge.gov.br;
14. www.elsevier.com;
15. www.regoverningmarkets.org/en;
16. www.elsevier.com;
17. www.tandfonline.com;
18. www.jae.exfordjournals.org;
19. www.elsevier.com;
20. www.fertizer.org